

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform

Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

[\(engr.anowar@yahoo.com\)](mailto:engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Online Publication: Third version, 13 July 2024

Keynote of report

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

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Keywords: Conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, PhD research, PhD obstacle, PhD harassment, Earning of a PhD researcher

This is a case report forwarded to Australian Ombudsman for ethical support of unethical PhD suspension and unethical PhD scholarship suspension(Hossain, 2023ca).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194679>

Official act of hidden life threatening and conspiracy of killing PhD candidate was tried to convince/hide through the executive suspension of PhD school. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced financial hardship in terms of scholarship honour versus honour of PhD degree versus unethical PhD suspension versus hidden life threatening versus killing conspiracy of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain versus unethical scholarship suspension versus harassment of genuine PhD research versus massacre the reputation of PhD researcher, massacre the motivation of PhD researcher versus professorship of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye versus unethical achievement of professor in PhD school versus uncivilized practice in PhD school.

There are following tragedy of PhD candidate when PhD researcher was addicted to do PhD research funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye was also addicted to execute killing conspiracy of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate(Hossain, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh).

- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and life-long health impact of PhD candidate
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and research impact of PhD candidate
- Lacking of life long protection of PhD candidate and life threatening in Melbourne
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and; action and support to PhD candidate without support of PhD candidate
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased fooding allowance
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased residential allowance
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased medical allowance
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased the school facilities of research material
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and psychological harassment was continued
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and psychologist bullying was continued
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate, verbal threatening and PhD harassment was continued

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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engranowar06@gmail.com

➤ Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and technological hijacking were continued

In general, work time of a PhD researcher is unlimited from morning to evening, from family office to research office. The contribution/dedication of a PhD researcher cannot be compared with the right payment of money although there is no royalty income of a researcher. So worldwide demotivation of a researcher/scientist is a global headache when the global wheel of human surviving fully depends on the hardwork and lower paid journey of a researcher/scientist. In a PhD platform of RMIT University, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain worked around 50-60 hours/per week and sometimes it was also more and more from morning to evening.

- to satisfy PhD requirement as per Australian Quality of Research Framework
- to achieve a quality PhD degree (M. A. Hossain, 2021b; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022b; Hossain, 2023g, 2023ak, 2023al) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023g, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023ap, 2023at, 2023ay, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bm, 2023bx, 2023cj, 2023ck)
- to satisfy supervisors requirement(Hossain, 2023bc)
- to satisfy the requirement of RTP stipend scholarship
- to remove the action and support, first time & second time for one PhD degree
- to remove executive suspension as per school requirement(Hossain, 2023bn, 2023cl, 2023cm)
- to activate enrolment as per school requirement
- to eliminate psychologist bullying
- to satisfy study fitness requirement for one PhD degree.
- to satisfy the protection of PhD candidate against unethical achievement of Professor Rajiv Padhye in PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University(Hossain, 2023bx) (Hossain, 2023g, 2023ar, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bk, 2023bx) (Hossain, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023ca, 2023cg, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2024c)
- to satisfy the honour protection of PhD candidate against uncivilized practice of professor Rajiv Padhye in PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University(Hossain, 2023bx) (Hossain, 2023g, 2023ar, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bk, 2023bx) (Hossain, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023ca, 2023cg, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2024c)

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- to satisfy the life protection of PhD candidate against unethical achievement of professor Rajiv Padhye in PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University(Hossain, 2023bx) (Hossain, 2023g, 2023ar, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bk, 2023bx) (Hossain, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023ca, 2023cg, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2024c)

The duration of PhD research was conducted around 10037.5 hours at PhD school, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

$$= 55 \text{ hours} \times 182.5 \text{ weeks}$$

$$= 10037.5 \text{ hours}$$

Figure 1, Payment of a PhD researcher in Australia

Figure 1, total payment of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be around 501875AUD as per Australian compliance payment rate in Australia

$$= 10037.5 \text{ hours} \times 50\text{AUD}$$

$$= 501875\text{AUD}$$

Total value of RTP Stipend Scholarship is around 252666AUD, Total non-paid RTP Stipend Scholarship is around 31260AUD.

It can be summarized that I, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain worked and received around 50% less payment under the honour of PhD scholarship, under the honour of PhD degree, under the

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engranowar06@gmail.com

motivation of PhD degree. Every PhD researcher hardly works for his PhD degree under lower paid works in terms of scholarship honour and motivation of PhD honour. So, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get PhD degree when he completed two milestone examination under zero comments/without revision of PhD committee for PhD thesis improvement. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also requested for third milestone examination without any extension of time period when unethical executive suspension was continued and continued when psychologist bullying was continued and continued when scholarship suspension was continued and continued when life threatening complain was converted to executive suspension. If school/professor Rajiv Padhye is not giving me PhD degree, school/university/office of Professor Rajiv Padhye should pay me compliance amount of whole payment around 501875AUD under Australian compliance in Melbourne. I, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't receive genuine working/research allowance in PhD school as per Australian compliance, so I should get PhD degree when I worked full time for PhD degree instead of getting money. I highly invested for a PhD degree from RMIT University. I am still reporting to Australian Ombudsman/Australian lawyer/ Australian police/ Australian court and reporting for their attention, it is a harassment under an official PhD schooling platform. I also invested a lot of money, a lot of additional time for a PhD degree from RMIT University.

A PhD category researcher will only continue his research to satisfy Australian Quality of Research Framework. It is not a professional/academic duty of a PhD researcher to satisfy in another way. If it is necessary to satisfy Professor by paying additional money, university/government should pay more money to professor. If professor has financial crisis, it is not my official responsibility to support a professor, it is the responsibility of Australian education department in Australia.

Relevant Evidences

A contact with Supreme Court of Australia

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Yahoo/Sent

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Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:supportservices@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:12 AM

Dear officer,

Do you have ability to advice for going to Victorian supreme court as I faced life threatening and an executive suspension was imposed to convince/divert the issue of conspiracy of life-threatening, Presently I am residing offshore. I have financial crisis when I am a nonpaid researcher.

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:supportservices@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:17 AM

Dear officer,

I am also attaching a pdf copy regarding my allegation.

Thanks for your support.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; PhD Training (Fashion & Textiles), PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles) since 2010

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

For details biography and profile,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>, www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

A contact with Australian Police in Brunswick Police Station, A local Police Station behind School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Victim impact statement is being reported to Australian Court, Australian Police Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:23 AM

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BRUNSWICK-UNI-OIC <brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au>

To:Anowar Hossain

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:27 AM

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

Good afternoon,

I'm sorry to hear about your situation.

If you need Police urgently please contact 000.

Can you attend a Police station to report the matter?

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:38 AM

Thanks for your quick reply.

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Thanks

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; PhD Training (Fashion & Textiles), PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>, www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>

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A contact with Australian Police in Brunswick Police Station, A local Police Station behind School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 12:32 PM

Dear Officer,

I am also attaching online link of victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University.

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>

Thanks

Victim impact statement is being reported to Australian Court, Australian Police

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:23 AM

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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Dear officer,

do you have ability to advice for going to Victorian supreme court as I faced life threatening and an executive suspension was imposed to convince/divert the issue of conspiracy of life-threatening, Presently I am residing offshore. I have financial crisis when I am a nonpaid researcher.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; PhD Training (Fashion & Textiles), PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

For details biography and profile,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>, www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

BRUNSWICK-UNI-OIC <brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:27 AM

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

Good afternoon,

I'm sorry to hear about your situation.

If you need Police urgently please contact 000.

Can you attend a Police station to report the matter?

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

From: Anowar Hossain <enqr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Sent: Thursday, 17 August 2023 3:24 PM

To: BRUNSWICK-UNI-OIC <BRUNSWICK.UNI@police.vic.gov.au>

Subject: Victim impact statement is being reported to Australian Court, Australian Police

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:28 AM

Dear Officer,

I am attaching a pdf file for details of my statement for your support.

This is a case report forwarded to Australian Ombudsman for ethical support of unethical PhD suspension and unethical PhD scholarship suspension(Hossain, 2023ac).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194679>

Official act of hidden life threatening and conspiracy of killing PhD candidate was tried to convince/hide through the executive suspension of PhD school. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced financial hardship in terms of scholarship honour versus honour of PhD degree versus unethical PhD suspension versus hidden life threatening versus killing conspiracy of PhD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain versus unethical scholarship suspension versus harassment of genuine PhD research versus massacre the reputation of PhD researcher, massacre the motivation of PhD researcher versus professorship of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye versus unethical achievement of professor in PhD school versus uncivilized practice in PhD school.

There are following tragedy of PhD candidate when PhD researcher was addicted to do PhD research funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye was also addicted to execute killing conspiracy of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate(Hossain, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x).

- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and life-long health impact of PhD candidate
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and research impact of PhD candidate
- Lacking of life long protection of PhD candidate and life threatening in Melbourne
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and; action and support to PhD candidate without support of PhD candidate
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased fooding allowance
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased residential allowance
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased medical allowance
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate was continued and ceased the school facilities of research material
- Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and psychological harassment was continued

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engranowar06@gmail.com

➤ **Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and psychologist bullying was continued**

➤ **Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate, verbal threatening and PhD harassment was continued**

➤ **Killing conspiracy of PhD candidate and technological hijacking were continued**

In general, work time of a PhD researcher is unlimited from morning to evening, from family office to research office. The contribution/dedication of a PhD researcher cannot be compared with the right payment of money although there is no royalty income of a researcher. So worldwide demotivation of a researcher/scientist is a global headache when the global wheel of human surviving fully depends on the hardwork and lower paid journey of a researcher/scientist. In a PhD platform of RMIT University, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain worked around 50-60 hours/per week and sometimes it was also more and more from morning to evening.

➤ **to satisfy PhD requirement as per Australian Quality of Research Framework**

➤ **to achieve a quality PhD degree (M. A. Hossain, 2021b; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022b; Hossain, 2023c, 2023f, 2023g) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023n, 2023o, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ae, 2023af)**

➤ **to satisfy supervisors requirement(Hossain, 2023s)**

➤ **to satisfy the requirement of RTP stipend scholarship**

➤ **to remove the action and support, first time & second time for one PhD degree**

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- to remove executive suspension as per school requirement(Hossain, 2023ag, 2023ah)
- to activate enrolment as per school requirement
- to eliminate psychologist bullying
- to satisfy study fitness requirement for one PhD degree.
- to satisfy the protection of PhD candidate against unethical achievement of Professor Rajiv Padhye in PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University(Hossain, 2023b) (Hossain, 2023b, 2023c, 2023k, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023aa) (Hossain, 2023j, 2023l, 2023m, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ag, 2023ah)
- to satisfy the honour protection of PhD candidate against uncivilized practice of professor Rajiv Padhye in PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University(Hossain, 2023b) (Hossain, 2023b, 2023c, 2023k, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023aa) (Hossain, 2023j, 2023l, 2023m, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ag, 2023ah)
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The duration of PhD research was conducted around 10037.5 hours at PhD school, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

= 55 hours × 182.5 weeks

= 10037.5 hours

Figure 1, Payment of a PhD researcher in Australia

Figure 1, total payment of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be around 501875AUD as per Australian compliance payment rate in Australia

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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
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 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

= 10037.5 hours x 50AUD

= 501875AUD

Total value of RTP Stipend Scholarship is around 252666AUD, Total non-paid RTP Stipend Scholarship is around 31260AUD.

It can be summarized that I, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain worked and received around 50% less payment under the honour of PhD scholarship, under the honour of PhD degree, under the motivation of PhD degree. Every PhD researcher hardly works for his PhD degree under lower paid works in terms of scholarship honour and motivation of PhD honour. So, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get PhD degree when he completed two milestone examination under zero comments/without revision of PhD committee for PhD thesis improvement. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also requested for third milestone examination without any extension of time period when unethical executive suspension was continued and continued when psychologist bullying was continued and continued when scholarship suspension was continued and continued when life threatening complain was converted to executive suspension. If school/professor Rajiv Padhye is not giving me PhD degree, school/university/office of Professor Rajiv Padhye should pay me compliance amount of whole payment around 501875AUD under Australian compliance in Melbourne. I, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't receive genuine working/research allowance in PhD school as per Australian compliance, so I should get PhD degree when I worked full time for PhD degree instead of getting money. I highly invested for a PhD degree from RMIT University. I am still reporting to Australian Ombudsman/Australian lawyer/ Australian police/ Australian court and reporting for their attention, it is a harassment under an official PhD schooling platform. I also invested a lot of money, a lot of additional time for a PhD degree from RMIT University.

A PhD category researcher will only continue his research to satisfy Australian Quality of Research Framework. It is not a professional/academic duty of a PhD researcher to satisfy in another way.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

If it is necessary to satisfy Professor by paying additional money, university/government should pay more money to professor. If professor has financial crisis, it is not official responsibility to support a professor, it is the responsibility of Australian education department in Australia.

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne,*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

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BRUNSWICK-UNI-OIC <brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Thu, Sep 7 at 3:54 AM

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

Good morning Anowar,

As per the advice you have been provided with this is not a matter Victoria Police can assist with. I suggest you go through the Ombudsman as previously advised or perhaps the education department

Kind regards

Fiona PARVIN | Acting Senior Sergeant 25250 - General Duties | Brunswick

email: fiona.parvin@police.vic.gov.au | web address: www.police.vic.gov.au
phone: (03) 8378 6000 | fax: (03) 8378 6060 | address: **630 Sydney Road, Brunswick 3056**

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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engranowar06@gmail.com

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.2

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:supportservices@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:12 AM

Dear Officer,

Do you have ability to advice for going to Victorian supreme court as I faced life threatening and an executive suspension was imposed to convince/divert the issue of conspiracy of life-threatening, Presently I am residing offshore. I have financial crisis when I am a nonpaid researcher.

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:supportservices@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:17 AM

Dear Officer,

I am also attaching a pdf copy regarding my allegation.

Thanks for your support.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; PhD Training (Fashion & Textiles), PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

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To:Complaints

Thu, Aug 17 at 10:54 AM

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Craig Hamilton (he/him)
Investigation Officer

Thanks for your response from the office of Victorian Ombudsman

I am confused that if you cannot consider the situation of victim why do you like to receive complain through online form.

However, do you have ability to advice for going to Victorian court as I faced life threatening and an executive suspension was imposed to convince/divert the issue of conspiracy of life-threatening when I am residing offshore.

your approach about RMIT University - C/23/160592

Yahoo/Sent

Complaints <complaints@ombudsman.vic.gov.au>

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Thu, Aug 17 at 10:15 AM

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Thank you for your approach about RMIT University and for providing further information for assessment.

You raise concerns about an enrolment matter.

The Ombudsman can consider complaints about the university under the *Ombudsman Act 1973* (Vic). The Ombudsman is independent and does not represent any of the parties involved. Whilst we consider all complaints received, not all complaints will proceed to enquiries or investigation.

The Ombudsman's office may become involved in a complaint where we believe the agency in question made a decision it was not allowed to make or was unreasonable when following the relevant processes and procedures. The Ombudsman is not a court and is unable to directly overturn a decision that has been made or to compel another decision to be made in its place.

In responding to your matter on 5 July 2022, the Academic Registrar wrote to you advising you are to be executively suspended until further notice.

RMIT explained the reasons for its decision and say your actions and behaviours are high risk misconduct. The decision was approved by the Deputy Vice-Chancellor of Education, and you were invited to email academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au with any questions.

The Deputy Academic Registrar wrote to you on 26 July 2023 referring to email correspondence sent to you from the Office of the Academic Registrar on 18 July 2023.

In the response the Registrar says they;

Acknowledged the fitness to study mental health risk assessment process previously communicated to you by Safer Community and the RMIT Counselling and Mental Health Service in September and November 2022 (as the requisite process to seek revocation of the executive suspension);

Acknowledged your written submission dated 30 June 2023 purporting to establish your fitness to return to study noting that it did not satisfy the assessment process requirements;

and Provided you with an additional 7 days to demonstrate engagement with the fitness to study mental health risk assessment process, noting that failure to do so by close of business on 25 July 2023 would exhaust your final opportunity to undergo the assessment.

You made a further written submission on 22 July 2023 which again did not satisfy the assessment process requirements and did not demonstrate engagement with the assessment process previously communicated to you.

The Registrar explained ;

RMIT followed the Student Conduct Regulations, executive suspensions continue to operate for a period of 12 months from the date of imposition. As your

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executive suspension was effective from the date of the notice provided to you on 5 July 2022, your executive suspension expired on 5 July 2023. In accordance with clause 32 of the Student Conduct Regulations, as you have not demonstrated within 12 months of the executive suspension (and the additional 7-day period provided) that you are fit to return to study or otherwise engage with RMIT without further risk (via the requisite assessment process), your program enrolment and PhD candidature has now been cancelled. I do not consider RMIT to have erred in responding to your complaint.

Our office does not have the ability to direct RMIT to reach a different decision about this. We cannot achieve the outcome you are seeking for you.

RMIT has responded to you explaining its consideration of your matter, I do not consider additional enquiries by our office are likely to change the situation.
Yours sincerely

Craig

Craig Hamilton (he/him)
Investigation Officer

Phone: +61 3 9613 6222 | Toll Free: 1800 806 314
Fax: +61 3 9602 4761
Level 2, 570 Bourke Street, Melbourne, VIC 3000
<https://www.ombudsman.vic.gov.au>

Victim impact statement is being reported to Australian Court, Australian Police

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:23 AM

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Show original message

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507.2kB

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 11:38 AM

Thanks for your quick reply.

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Thanks

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Page | 31

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: hotline@nationalsecurity.gov.au, front.desk@aic.gov.au, NOSSC-Canberra@afp.gov.au, v@police.vic.gov.au, brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au

Fri, Aug 25 at 6:03 PM

Dear Police Officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>

RE: Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University [SEC=OFFICIAL]

Yahoo/Inbox

NOSSC-CANBERRA <nossc-canberra@afp.gov.au>

To:Anowar Hossain

Sat, Aug 26 at 2:18 AM

OFFICIAL

Good morning Mr Hossain,

Reference is made to your email to the Australian Federal Police.

The AFP is the primary law enforcement agency responsible for investigating crimes against the Commonwealth of Australia. Information about what the AFP may investigate and the processes involved can be found at <http://www.afp.gov.au/contact/report-a-crime>.

From the information you have provided, the issues raised does not fall within the remit of the AFP

If you have not already done so, you may wish to consider reporting this matter to your local law enforcement agency and request they make enquiries through INTERPOL channels.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing
Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing,
Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in
Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research
Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile
Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law,
Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation,
Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting; Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher
Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer;
Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Your correspondence has been recorded by the AFP; however, no further action will be taken at this time.

Kind regards,

NOSSC - Canberra
National Operations State Service Centre
www.afp.gov.au

A contact with Supreme Court of Australia

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: media@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 12:42 PM

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Dear officer,

I am also attaching online link of victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University.

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>

Thanks

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:media@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 12:47 PM

Dear Officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Thanks

Seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Yahoo/Sen

A contact with Australian Country Court

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

To:communications@countycourt.vic.gov.au

Fri, Aug 25 at 6:48 PM

Dear Police Officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-](#)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

[sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Anowar Hossain <enagr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:communications@countycourt.vic.gov.au

Fri, Aug 25 at 6:51 PM

Please note that the heading will be court officer instead of police officer

seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enagr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:srl@countycourt.vic.gov.au

Fri, Aug 25 at 7:04 PM

Dear court officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

(PDF) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively low...

PDF | Key note of report This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au)...

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:judgemesexton.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au

Cc:Vice Chancellor

Fri, Aug 25 at 7:18 PM

Her Honour Judge M Sexton

Deputy Chief Judge

Dear Judge,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting; Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Page | 41

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:chiefjudge.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au

Cc:Vice Chancellor

Fri, Aug 25 at 7:15 PM

His Honour Chief Judge Kidd

Chief Judge

Dear Judge,

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:judgebayles.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,judgeblair.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,ju
dgempbourke.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,judgeklbourke.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.a

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

u,judgebrimer.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeburchell.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecahill.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecain.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecannon.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecarlin.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecarlmody.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgechambers.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeclark.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeclayton.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecois.h.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgecosgrave.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetalzie.l.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
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judgetadempsey.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
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judgetadyer.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeellis.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeenglish.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgefraatz.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgegamble.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgegaynor.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeholding.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgejohns.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgekarapanagiotidis.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgekelly.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeleighfield.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelyon.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
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judgetemullaly.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
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judgetewraight.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgeteallen.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetebowman.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetebrookes.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetechettle.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
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judgetelmason.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelmcinerney.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelmissis.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelmurphy.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelsmallwood.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelsmith.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelsyme.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
judgetelwilmoth.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,
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judgeteljudicialregistrarbales.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au

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vic.gov.au,CommercialJR.Chambers@courts.vic.gov.au,jrgurry.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,commercialjr.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,judicialregistrarphillips.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,judicialregistrarwilson.chambers@countycourt.vic.gov.au,lachlan.sharp@countycourt.vic.gov.au,dennis.thomas@countycourt.vic.gov.au,jason.goliszek@countycourt.vic.gov.au,criminal.division.administrators@countycourt.vic.gov.au,DivisionLawyer@countycourt.vic.gov.auHide

Cc:Vice Chancellor,Md Hossain

Fri, Aug 25 at 8:03 PM

Your honour

Dear Judge,

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Best Regards

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Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Enqr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

RE: seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right

Yahoo/Inbox

CSV-CCV-SRL (CSV) <srl@countycourt.vic.gov.au>

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

To: Anowar Hossain

Tue, Aug 29 at 11:35 AM

Dear Anowar,

We are unsure what you are seeking information on in your email. You can review our website [here](#) on how cases are initiated in the County Court of Victoria.

Legal assistance

You may wish to access the Law Institute of Victoria's 'Find Your Lawyer Referral Service.'

The service will refer you to a private lawyer in your area that specialises in the area of law that you need, and you can obtain an initial consultation of up to 30 minutes for free. You can obtain up to three referral letters to lawyers that have agreed to see clients for up to the first 30 minutes free of charge.

You can obtain this referral by either:

- Calling them on the number **03 9607 9550 Monday to Friday, 9-5pm**
- Via their website [Referral Search \(liv.asn.au\)](http://liv.asn.au)

Kind regards,

Case Manager – Self-Represented Litigants

County Court of Victoria

250 William Street, Melbourne, VIC 3000

T 03 8636 6528 | E srl@countycourt.vic.gov.au

www.countycourt.vic.gov.au

A contact with CEO, Supreme Court of Australia

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

To:CEO-office@supcourt.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 12:50 PM

Dear officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform

A contact with Australian Education Department

Online enquiry received - Response ID: R_3gc1hwMVOMx89LH

Yahoo/Inbox

•
Department of Education <noreply@qemailserver.com>

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing
Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of
Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing,
Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in
Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research
Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile
Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law,
Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation,
Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher
Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer;
Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of
Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology,
Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
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Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thu, Aug 17 at 5:40 PM

Thank you for submitting your online enquiry to the Department of Education.

The department will respond to you shortly.

Please see the details of your enquiry below:

Submitted: August 17, 2023 9:40 PM

Response ID: R_3gc1hwMVOMx89LH

I would like help with: 5

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Email address: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Phone number: 0452209738

Student ID: 3820066

Provider ID:

Main enquiry details:

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University Dear Officer, The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly. PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform Thanks

Do you wish to be contacted? Yes I want to be contacted

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court/Department of education for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enagr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:complaints@education.gov.au

Fri, Aug 25 at 5:40 PM

Dear officer,

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCME College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Please go through this link for details

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCME College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.

Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enagr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enagr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

A contact with Australian Education Department

Complaint received: Other, please specify:Cancellation of PhD suspension and PhD enrolment under official act of life threatening and conspiracy of hidden life-threatening |

Yahoo/Inbox

Australian Government Department of Education <noreply@qemailserver.com>

To:enagr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thu, Aug 17 at 5:24 PM

Hi Md. Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for submitting your complaint to the Department of Education. The department will respond to you shortly.

Please see the details of your enquiry below.

Submitted: August 17, 2023 9:24 PM

Privacy Statement: Consent and acknowledgment

I confirm that I have read and understood the privacy statement above and agree to the department handling my personal information in accordance with this privacy statement.

Complaint Category:

Other, please specify: Cancellation of PhD suspension and PhD enrolment under official act of life threatening and conspiracy of hidden life-threatening |

Name (First name, Last name) * : Md. Anowar Hossain

Phone: 0452209738

Email * : engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Home Address:

Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur, (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh
1990

Please provide details of your complaint:

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University Dear Officer, The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly. PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform Thanks

Attachment (if any):

PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree.pdf

https://submit.dese.gov.au/WRQualtricsSurveyEngine/File.php?F=F_2fwZW7k57FKPN3Z

FW: Department of Education online contact form - New enquiry received (R_3gc1hwMVOMx89LH) [SEC=OFFICIAL]

Yahoo/Inbox

Education - International Students <international.students@education.gov.au>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Mon, Sep 4 at 9:04 AM

Dear Md. Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for your email to the Australia Government's Department of Education. We apologise for the delay in responding to your query.

The Victorian Ombudsman may be able to assist you. They can investigate complaints from international students about public schools, colleges, institutes, and universities in Australia.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
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MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

You can provide information about your problems at RMIT at <https://www.ombudsman.vic.gov.au/>.

We hope this information is helpful to you.

Kind regards,

International Students Mailbox

Australian Government Department of Education

[Website](#) | [Twitter](#) | [LinkedIn](#) | [Facebook](#) | [Newsroom](#)

The Department of Education acknowledges the traditional owners and custodians of country throughout Australia and their continuing connection to land, waters and community. We pay our respects to them and their cultures, and Elders past, present and emergin

FW: Department of Education online contact form - New enquiry received (R_3gc1hwMVOMx89LH) [SEC=OFFICIAL]2

Yahoo/Sent

Education - International Students

Dear Md. Anowar Hossain, Thank you for your email to the Australia Government's Department of Education. We apologise for the delay in responding to your query. The Victorian Ombudsman may be able to assist you. They can investigate complaints from international students about public schools, colleges, institutes, and universities in Australia. You can provide information about your problems at RMIT at <https://www.ombudsman.vic.gov.au/>. We hope this information is helpful to you. Kind regards, Internation

Mon, Sep 4 at 9:04 AM

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Education - International Students

Cc: Vice Chancellor, Safer Community, Lijing Wang, Robert Shanks, Robert Shanks, SGR Scholarships, Md Hossain, Scott Mayson, Sean Ryan, SHADI HOUSHYAR, Steve Michielsen, Saniyat Islam, Shelley MacRae, Sarah Palmer, student.rights@rmit.edu.au, calum Drummond, Denise Cuthbert, David Castle, DVC R&I, dvcr@rmit.com.au, alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au, Andrea Eckersley, alice.payne@rmit.edu.au, Academic Registrar, amber.douglas@rmit.edu.au, RMIT Connect, Xin Wang, robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au, rusu@rmit.edu.au, Complaints, Grants, gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au, B RUNSWICK-UNI-OIC, mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au, engranowar06@gmail.com, hotline@nationalecurity.gov.au, Nahid Islam, RMIT University, NOSSC-CANBERRA, researchfellowships@rmit.edu.au, complaintsadvice@rmit.edu.au Hide

Wed, Sep 6 at 12:47 PM

Executive Officer

Education Department

Government of Australia

Dear Executive Officer,

I refer your e-mail in below.

Thanks for your assessment of victim impact statement and recommendation for going to Victorian Ombudsman. I also got same recommendation from the office of safer community, RMIT University and office of academic registrar, RMIT University. I have attached my reporting to "Victorian Ombudsman and assessment result". The officer of ombudsman also quoted and advised "**The Ombudsman is not a court and is unable to directly overturn a decision that has been made or to compel another decision to be made in its place**". Ombudsman polished, accumulated and summarized the decision of RMIT University. Ombudsman didn't make any summarization of the allegation of student issue. I am little bit confused about the letter of ombudsman. I need to know an organization in Australia who can polish and summarize the allegation of PhD student. I need to ask the name of an organization in Australia who can polish and summarize the allegation of PhD student. I need to ask a name of website which can direct the right conduct of a

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Professor in Australia (My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement o...

Key note of PhD case letter This is a case report of PhD candidate for education lawyers, criminal lawyers, hu...

But going to court is expensive journey, a harassment journey for an international student, an artificial trapping for a PhD scholar. What is the state of your office to make it ethical if it is possible to solve without court if it is possible to solve through the administration of education department when I am sufferer and sufferer? I also asked for support to school administration, RMIT University on 24 January 2022. I also asked for lawyer support to RMIT University on 24 January 2022. May I seek the right support of victim through Australian government lawyer. It is also necessary to ensure an approved flow chart for the right support of PhD student for achieving a PhD degree when I have written a lot of e-mail to every concern of Australian government when I have no funding for fooding and residential allowance to communicate accordingly.

Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University;

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>

[Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under](#)

Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethic...

Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship...

Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD

School. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320778>

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

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Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of
presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the
world]

Seeking the support of Education Department/Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: esos@rmit.edu.au

Fri, Aug 25 at 6:29 PM

Dear Officer,

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

(PDF) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively low...

PDF | Key note of report This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au)...

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

A contact with Australian Police

Reported Matter

Yahoo/Inbox

White, Taylor <taylor.white@police.vic.gov.au>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Thu, Aug 17 at 2:21 PM

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

Good Evening,

I have been made aware of your report regarding your PHD suspension.

How can I best help you today regarding the matter?

Regards,

Taylor WHITE | First Constable 46895

Brunswick Uniform | North West 4 | Victoria Police

Email: Taylor.White@police.vic.gov.au Phone: 8378 6000

Address: 630 Sydney Road, Brunswick | DX: 211503

OFFICIAL: Sensitive

=====
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Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: BRUNSWICK-UNI-OIC

Cc: Vice Chancellor

Sun, Aug 27 at 1:09 PM

Police Commissioner

Melbourne

Victoria

Dear Police Commissioner,

Referred to previous e-mail notification from my office, I have attached below e-mail of Australian Federal Police along with the below link of victim statement.

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>

Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974> (full notarized scanned copy)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street

Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schoolin...

PhD education and research plays a vital role for the society development. The life-threatening, hidden life-thr...

RE: Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University [SEC=OFFICIAL]

Yahoo/Inbox

- NOSSC-CANBERRA <nossc-canberra@afp.gov.au>

To:Anowar Hossain

Sat, Aug 26 at 2:18 AM

OFFICIAL

Good morning Mr Hossain,

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Reference is made to your email to the Australian Federal Police.

The AFP is the primary law enforcement agency responsible for investigating crimes against the Commonwealth of Australia. Information about what the AFP may investigate and the processes involved can be found at <http://www.afp.gov.au/contact/report-a-crime>.

From the information you have provided, the issues raised does not fall within the remit of the AFP

If you have not already done so, you may wish to consider reporting this matter to your local law enforcement agency and request they make enquiries through INTERPOL channels.

Your correspondence has been recorded by the AFP; however, no further action will be taken at this time.

Kind regards,

NOSSC - Canberra
National Operations State Service Centre
www.afp.gov.au

Thanks for your every action.

A contact with Victoria Legal Aid of Australia

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:03 PM

Dear officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; [PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Automatic reply: Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Inbox

Grants <grants@vla.vic.gov.au>

To:Anowar Hossain

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:03 PM

Thank you for your email. We are experiencing a delay in assessing applications for aid, including extensions and transfer requests. We apologise for this delay and thank you for your patience during this time.

Assessment priorities

We are prioritizing court ordered funding and assistance for urgent matters, including:

- criminal trials
- family law matters with either FDRS conference or hearing dates within the next 5 days (excludes mentions, directions hearings and other procedural hearings)
- civil law applications with hearing dates within the next 5 days
- matters in the Court of Appeal and the High Court
- public interest and strategic litigation (PISL) matters
- requests for Senior Counsel, two Counsel and requests for large amounts of additional preparation
- requests for expert reports in major criminal cases
- matters with imminent dates for filing materials for Cth family law final hearings (where resources permit)

To assist us to focus our efforts on prioritising urgent matters and reduce the delay, we ask that you please limit your enquiries about applications for legal assistance to matters with an imminent court date. **Please note** that requests for status updates may not receive a response given our priorities.

Help us to respond to your enquiries quicker

We also ask that you please use the following format when sending emails so we can respond as quickly as possible:

- **Subject Field:** [next court date] [type of hearing e.g. mention/hearing/trial/appeal] [file reference] [client's full name] [type of matter e.g. summary/indictable/family/FDRS/ICL/child protection/civil]
- **Body of text** (brief dot points): What is your enquiry? Is it urgent – if so, why?

Legal Help

If you do not have a grant of legal aid and want information on a legal problem, please contact Victoria Legal Aid's (VLA) Legal Help phoneline for free information about the law and how VLA can help you. Legal Help can be contacted on 1300 792 387, Monday to Friday, 8am to 6pm

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

(excluding public holidays). Legal Help also offers a free online chat service for general information and referrals, which operates Monday to Friday, 9am to 5pm, subject to availability. You can access Legal Help Chat from the VLA website: www.legalaid.vic.gov.au

If you are a panel practitioner

If you are a practitioner with a query about how to use ATLAS, or how our Guidelines or Fees apply, please first visit [VLA - GQA Training Videos \(vimeopro.com\)](http://VLA-GQA-Training-Videos(vimeopro.com)), where we have developed a series of training resources to assist you. If you have any questions about these modules, please email grantstraining@vla.vic.gov.au.

Victoria Legal Aid's website makes it easier for all Victorians to find services and information to help with their legal problem. Visit www.legalaid.vic.gov.au.

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Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Mon, Aug 28 at 10:35 AM

Victoria Legal Aid
Melbourne, Australia

Dear Officer,

I refer to below attached e-mail.

I want to commence a court file against Professor Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles and Vice Chancellor, RMIT University.

I telephoned (0061393005333) on 28 August 2023 at 3:10 Pm to your sunshine, Melbourne Branch. I introduced myself with Name, name spelling, date of birth, present location etc. I asked and explained for the support of court commencement/right support.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting; Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Concern officer told me that Victoria Aid has no financial support for such type of court commencement. Officer recommended for private lawyers. I am totally helpless regarding the issue when I am not getting salary from RMIT University.

I have also attached evidences of my PhD harassment and a breach of Australian Schooling.

Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; [Video Report to school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University for removal of PhD suspension Part 2](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=86cxLN3Z9ro)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Video Report to school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University for remov...

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286821>

May I seek every ethical support when I have ethical voice as part of mankind when I have ethical voice for the peace of mankind.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
enqr.anowar06@gmail.com

Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.

Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

**Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of
presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world**

Anowar Hossain <enqr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Mon, Aug 28 at 11:23 AM

Dear officer,

I am also forwarding evidences of PhD harassment.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>;

Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

Hossain, M. A. (2023be). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; [My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School \(Part-06\)](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396)

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement o...

Author, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got Australian Government RTP stipend scholarship to pursue PhD in RMIT Univers...

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

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www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Grants <grants@vla.vic.gov.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Tue, Aug 29 at 3:50 AM

OFFICIAL

Thank you for your email.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Should you require a grant of legal assistance, please complete and return the attached application form for a grant of legal assistance to grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Kind regards,

Victoria Legal Aid

Show original message

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Grants

Wed, Sep 6 at 12:16 PM

Chief Executive Officer

Victoria Legal Aid

Dear officer,
Please being attached an application of legal support for your approval and necessary action of your office.

A contact with Australian Education Department

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:complaints@education.gov.au,prisms@education.gov.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 4:57 PM

Dear officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform

Thanks

A contact with Australian Bar Association

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:contact@austbar.asn.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 2:08 PM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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engranowar06@gmail.com

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Thanks

RE: Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University [SEC=OFFICIAL] [SEC=OFFICIAL:Sensitive, ACCESS=Personal-Privacy]

Yahoo/Inbox

Education - Prisms <prisms@education.gov.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Fri, Aug 18 at 6:16 AM

OFFICIAL:

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Sensitive//Personal Privacy

Dear Anowar,

Thank you for your email. Please note that PRISMS helpdesk does not deal with complaints or grievances raised by international students. When the student has a Confirmation of Enrolment (CoE) and is studying at a CRICOS registered provider, the student may be covered by the [Education Services for Overseas Students Act 2000](#) and the [National Code of Practice for Providers of Education and Training to Overseas Students 2018](#), with the following avenues available for raising a complaint or grievance:

- Since you are referring to PhD then the Higher Education avenue is to pursue – If you feel the provider has not met its requirements as a provider of education services, complaints can be lodged with the relevant education regulator – in this case the Tertiary Education Quality and Standards Agency (TEQSA) via its complaints form: [Raising a complaint or concern - online form | Tertiary Education Quality and Standards Agency \(teqsa.gov.au\)](#) Please read the guidance from TEQSA before lodging a complaint [Raising a complaint or concern | Tertiary Education Quality and Standards Agency \(teqsa.gov.au\)](#)

You can also lodge a complaint with [Student Ombudsman](#) as they deal with international students complaints. Please read the guidance from Ombudsman before you lodging a complaint: [How to make a complaint | Commonwealth Ombudsman](#). They are able to advise/assist and suggest the best possible course of action.

Kind regards,

System Support Officer
PRISMS Helpdesk

*ESOS Systems and Support | International Quality Branch
International Division
Australian Government Department of Education
Opportunity through learning
www.education.gov.au*

Supreme Court-Unrepresented Litigants <unrepresented@supcourt.vic.gov.au>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Fri, Aug 18 at 5:45 AM

Dear Anowar,

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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

You have recently emailed the Supreme Court of Victoria where it appears that you seek to understand the process to commence a civil proceeding in this court.

For your assistance, see a guide to starting a civil proceeding, as linked below. You will note that template forms are available via the appendix on the final page of the guide –

https://www.supremecourt.vic.gov.au/sites/default/files/2023-04/start_a_civil_proceeding.pdf

All filing, and the payment of court fees, occurs on the electronic filing system called redcrest, see www.redcrest.com.au/ and not by email.

In relation to your legal issues it is strongly suggested that you seek to access legal advice.

See a list of legal advice options for your consideration – <https://www.supremecourt.vic.gov.au/going-to-court/representing-yourself/free-and-low-cost-legal-help>

Regards,

Self-Represented Litigants Coordinator
Supreme Court of Victoria
(03) 8600 2031

Updated Resources are available for the assistance of Self Represented Litigants at:

www.supremecourt.vic.gov.au/going-to-court/representing-yourself

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: inquiries@liv.asn.au

Fri, Aug 18 at 10:24 AM

Dear Lawyer,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:administration@fcl.org.au

Fri, Aug 18 at 11:25 AM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
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Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: media@vla.vic.gov.au

Fri, Aug 18 at 11:32 AM

Dear Lawyer,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

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A contact with High Court of Australia

Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:croggers@hcourt.gov.au

Sat, Aug 26 at 6:48 AM

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Carolyn Rogers
Senior Registrar
High Court of Australia

Dear Officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-](#)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

[sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting; Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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engranowar06@gmail.com

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Registry@hcourt.gov.au,Registry@hcourt.gov.au

Sat, Aug 26 at 6:28 AM

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

RE: Automatic reply: Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of con...

Yahoo/Inbox

Rosemary Musolino <rosemary.musolino@hcourt.gov.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Mon, Aug 28 at 5:29 AM

Dear Anowar Hossain,

I refer to your email below.

I would point out that the Justices of the High Court of Australia consider legal issues raised by parties in matters properly commenced within the jurisdiction of the Court.

However it would appear that the matters that you raise would not fall within the jurisdiction of the High Court.

I strongly suggest that you seek legal advice as to whether or not it is open to you to commence

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engranowar06@gmail.com

a proceeding in an appropriate court in Australia as it is not the function of the Registry or the Registrars to provide legal advice.

Yours faithfully,

Rosemary Musolino

Acting Senior Registrar | High Court of Australia | L17, 305 William Street | MELBOURNE VIC 3000
T (02) 6270 6805 | E rmusolino@hcourt.gov.au | W www.hcourt.gov.au

Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: enquiries@hcourt.gov.au

Sat, Aug 26 at 6:25 AM

Dear Officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

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Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law,
Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
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RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Automatic reply: Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspir...2

Yahoo/Sent

Carolyn Rogers <carolyn.rogers@hcourt.gov.au>

To:Anowar Hossain

Sat, Aug 26 at 6:51 AM

I will be on leave until Monday 18 September.

Hide original message

Please contact Rosemary Musolino, Acting Senior Registrar, by email at Rosemary.Musolino@hcourt.gov.au if you require any assistance during that time.

Carolyn Rogers
Senior Registrar
High Court of Australia

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Rosemary.Musolino@hcourt.gov.au

Sat, Aug 26 at 10:52 AM

Rosemary Musolino

Acting Senior Registrar

High Court of Australia

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Page | 95

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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
enranowar06@gmail.com

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Hide original message

On Saturday, August 26, 2023 at 06:51:29 AM GMT+6, Carolyn Rogers <carolyn.rogers@hcourt.gov.au> wrote:

I will be on leave until Monday 18 September.

Please contact Rosemary Musolino, Acting Senior Registrar, by email at Rosemary.Musolino@hcourt.gov.au if you require any assistance during that time.

Carolyn Rogers
Senior Registrar
High Court of Australia

Seeking the right involvement of High court of Australia regarding life-threatening conspiracy of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain against the conspiracy of life-threatening against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye against the unethical cancellation of PhD enrolment at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enagr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:crogers@hcourt.gov.au,Registry@hcourt.gov.au

Cc:Vice Chancellor,Robert Shanks,Lijing Wang,Md Hossain,Andrea Eckersley,Scott Mayson,Safer Community,Sean Ryan,SHADI HOUSHYAR,Steve Michielsen,Xin Wang,mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au,alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au,calum Drummond,Denise Cuthbert,Saniyat Islam,Shelley MacRae,SGR Scholarships,Sarah Palmer,RMIT Connect,robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au,rusu@rmit.edu.au,alice.payne@rmit.edu.au,engranowar06@gmail.com,Academic Registrar,dvcr@rmit.com.au,gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au,rtsscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.au,Robert Shanks,David Castle,RMIT University,researchfellowships@rmit.edu.au,complaintsadvise@rmit.edu.au,alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au,DVC R&I,repository@rmit.edu.au,student.rights@rmit.edu.au,SGR Candidature,Grants,ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au,mark.sanderson@rmit.edu.au,margaret.jollands@rmit.edu.au,jennifer.palmer2@rmit.edu.au,elena.pirogova@rmit.edu.au,namita.choudhury@rmit.edu.au,kevin.zhang@rmit.edu.au,james.scott@rmit.edu.au,reza.hoseinnezhad@rmit.edu.au,stuart.bateman@rmit.edu.au,sara.moridpour@rmit.edu.au,ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au,vso@dfat.gov.au,consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bdHide

Sun, Oct 15 at 1:08 PM

Chief Executive & Principal Registrar

High Court of Australia

Please being attached the invoice to approve free of cost hearing support.

Every allegation and victim impact statement has been attached for your kind approval. I have no lawyer, I have no money for court hearing but I can self-present whatever I reported by writing.

I have lodged following files in online system of High Court of Australia against the conspiracy of life-threatening against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye against the unethical cancellation of PhD enrolment at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University.

Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD

School. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320778>

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Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8394316>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>

Previous correspondence with High Court of Australia on 26 August 2023

Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Registry@hcourt.gov.au, Registry@hcourt.gov.au

Sat, Aug 26 at 6:28 AM

Dear Officer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh. Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

This report was forwarded to Brunswick police station (brunswick.uni@police.vic.gov.au), Melbourne, Australia for victim statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. It was requested to police officer for forwarding to Australian Supreme court in Australia. The life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, harassment and corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education and a continuous breaching of Australian PhD schooling. The unethical and hidden life-threatening has been focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. The matter was a long-term discussion process with RMIT university, a concern office of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University who tried to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher, School of fashion & Textiles, RMIT University again and again. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancelation of PhD enrolment. Therefore, Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking the support of Australian Supreme Court for right assessment and ensuring PhD degree of Md. Anowar Hossain, ensuring non-paid PhD scholarship when I worked full time under the discussion process of conspiracy of killing PhD candidate and right attachment with PhD supervisors, right submission of PhD reporting in PhD school.

Please go through this link for details

[\(PDF\) PhD scholarship is an honour, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

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City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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High Court of Australia

Parke Place
 Parke ACT 2600

TAX INVOICE

ABN: 69 445 188 986
 Phone: (02) 6270 6857
 Fax: (02) 6273 3025

Md. Anowar Hossain
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, VIC, 3056
 Melbourne Victoria 3056

Invoice date 15 Oct 2023

Your Reference: Invoice Number - HCAINV-08212

Item/Description	Qty	Fee	GST	Amount
Form 12 - Application for constitutional or other writ Md. Anowar Hossain v. Padhye (Lodgement Ref: LOD-008151) (Case :)	1.00	\$3,910.00	0.00	\$3,910.00
Total Amount:			0.00	\$3,910.00

All court fees are exempt from GST under Division 81, A New Tax System (Goods & Services Tax) Act 1999

Case is not considered filed until full payment is received by the Court

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EFT: Your payment can be directly deposited into our RBA Bank account
BSB: 092 009 Account Number: 919 398

The **Transaction ID must be quoted in the reference field** and email your remittance to Accounts@hcourt.gov.au
 Tax invoice becomes receipt on payment via EFT

This is a message from the High Court Registry.

Dear Sir,

Deputy Registrar Young notes the following matter,

Your lodgment does not include its initiating application, a Form 12 application for a constitutional or other writ. That document is essential. . Please refer to Part 25 of the High Court rules when making your application.

A concise affidavit in support of your application will need to address the requirements set out in rule 25.05. Evidence by Affidavit should be prepared in accordance with rule 24.01. Please also see the sample Affidavit available on the Court's website at https://www.hcourt.gov.au/assets/registry/Forms2023/Example_Affidavit-Form-2023.pdf

Copies of the prescribed forms for commencing a Form 12 application are available to download on the Court's website here: https://www.hcourt.gov.au/registry/filing-documents/registry_forms-2020. Please note that the rules of the court relevant to all High Court applications are the High Court Rules 2004 (Cth) (the Rules). You can access the Rules via a link on the Court's website here: <https://www.hcourt.gov.au/registry/filing-documents>. Understanding the Rules will assist you greatly in making any application to the Court.

Please also be advised that since January 2020, all documents are to be filed electronically through the Court's Digital Lodgment System (DLS). If you wish to commence proceedings in the High Court, you must first register as a user of the DLS. Further information on this process, and the DLS system generally, is available via the Court's website here: <https://www.hcourt.gov.au/digital-lodgment-system/digital-lodgment-system-information> .The following information sheets (available via the link) may be of particular assistance:

1. How to register for a DLS Portal User Account.
2. Frequently asked questions.

In relation to the fees payable for filing documents, detailed information is available via the Court's website here: <https://www.hcourt.gov.au/registry/filing-documents/high-court-of-australia-fees> . This includes information on eligibility and the process for applying for an exemption from filing and hearing fees and how to apply to pay the financial hardship fee. The forms required to apply for an exemption or payment of the financial hardship fee are also available through that link.

Please note that the above information is intended only as a procedural guide. It is recommended that intending applicants seek legal advice before commencing proceedings. In any event, intending applicants should familiarise themselves with the requirements of the High Court Rules 2004, in particular with Rule 25 and the relevant legislation relating to their application.

Accordingly your lodgment has been rejected. As a consequence of that rejection, it is not open to you to upload further documents on this lodgment. If it is open to you to do so and if you wish to lodge revised documents, you will need to create a new case and upload your documents to a fresh lodgment.

If you require any further assistance, please contact the Registry.

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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Kind Regards,

High Court Registry | High Court of Australia
T (02) 6270 6829 | E registry@hcourt.gov.au | W www.hcourt.gov.au

The Australian Honours and Awards Secretariat

Page | 105

The Australian Honours and Awards Secretariat

Government House

CANBERRA ACT 2600

Submission for the consideration of Australian Honours and Awards in early assessment year.

Your Excellency

I have attached a pdf copy with online link for consideration of Australian Honours and Awards in early assessment year.

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. ([PDF](#)) [Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University](#)

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(PDF) Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first versi...

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Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first ve...

The invention of PhD thesis has camouflage theory, color engineering, camouflage engineering, camouflage materia...

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thanks

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

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(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

RE: Submission for the consideration of Australian Honours and Awards in early assessment year [SEC=OFFICIAL]

Yahoo/Inbox

(Shared) Australian Honours Secretariat <honours@gg.gov.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Mon, Aug 28 at 8:57 AM

Dear Professor Hossain

Thank you for your correspondence regarding making an Order of Australia nomination.

Nominations need to be submitted through an online portal. Users will log in, be able to save and work on nominations before they complete and submit. They will also be able to monitor the status of a nomination from submission to completion.

We encourage you to register and complete your nomination through our online portal which can be found here: <https://www.gg.gov.au/australian-honours-and-awards/nominate-someone-award>

Kind regards

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Australian Honours and Awards Secretariat
Office of the Official Secretary to the Governor-General
Government House, Canberra ACT 2600
T: +61 2 6283 3604
W: www.gg.gov.au
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Reported to Australian Competition and Consumer Commission

We received your report

Thank you for taking the time to let us know about this issue. We've sent you an email with all the details you shared.

Your business report number: **accs-smb:600467**

What happens next?

- We'll read your report.
- We'll use the information you shared to understand which issues are causing the most harm to Australians and to help focus our resources.
- If we have information that may be helpful to you, we'll be in touch within 15 business days.

For further information about your options:

- learn about your [rights and responsibilities](#) as a small business
- if you're in franchising, read our [franchising guidance](#)

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- contact your state's [Small Business Commissioner](#)
- contact the [Australian Small Business and Family Enterprise Ombudsman](#)
- you may need to consider seeking independent legal advice.

We received your report

Yahoo/Inbox

Do Not Reply ACCC <do_not_reply@accc.gov.au>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sat, Aug 26 at 3:48 PM

Thank you for taking the time to let us know about this issue

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engranowar06@gmail.com

- contact your state's [Small Business Commissioner](#)
- contact the [Australian Small Business and Family Enterprise Ombudsman](#)
- you may need to consider seeking independent legal advice.

ACCC Response (Reference: REF4310979) [SEC=OFFICIAL]

Page | 111

Yahoo/Inbox

Infocentre Public Mailbox <info.centre@accc.gov.au>

To: REF4310979 Md. Anowar Hossain

Fri, Sep 15 at 6:56 AM

Dear Md. Anowar

Thank you for writing to us. We have recorded the details of your report. Below is some information that we hope you will find helpful.

From the information you have provided, the concerns you have raised appear to fall outside of the laws we administer. The Australian Consumer Law provides Australians with broad consumer protections including the right to truthful and accurate representations, fair treatment and consumer guarantees. You can [read more about consumer rights](#) on our website. If you have information that you believe may indicate a breach of these laws, we welcome you to submit it to us.

State, territory and local governments, and the laws we administer

The laws we manage apply to state, territory and local government bodies only when they are carrying on business activities. When they are conducting their normal functions—like imposing taxes or issuing licences—the laws we administer do not apply to them.

If you feel that a public university has acted inappropriately, you should try to resolve the matter with them directly. You can use the [directory.gov.au](#) website to [find out how to contact state, territory and local government bodies](#).

If you cannot resolve the matter with the government body, you should [contact the government ombudsman in your state or territory](#).

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Your report: what the ACCC does with this information

The ACCC uses reports from the public, as well as other sources of intelligence, to inform our enforcement work. You can [read more about how we prioritise our work](#) on our website.

Please note, the ACCC generally does not comment on our work or what we do with the information we receive from reports. We will only contact you again if we require further information.

To keep up-to-date on public announcements from the ACCC, you can [subscribe to our email alerts](#).

We hope the information we have provided is helpful.

Yours sincerely

Rowan

Public Information Officer | Infocentre
Australian Competition and Consumer Commission
23 Marcus Clarke Street Canberra 2601 | www.accc.gov.au
T: 1300 302 502

[@acccgovau](#)

[ACCCConsumerRights](#)

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A communication with PhD supervisor

Seeking letter for extension of study leave or a letter of PhD achievement to continue my teaching job in Bangladesh

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Robert Shanks, Robert Shanks

Cc: Lijing Wang

Sun, Aug 27 at 12:34 PM

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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Dear Professor Robert,

As per discussion with Professor Lijing, his e-mail ID (lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au) is blocked now and he is not receiving my e-mail.

Page | 113

May I seek a letter for extension of my study leave to complete my PhD under your supervision. My study leave is going to finish by September 2023.

If you don't allow my PhD study leave, Please send me a letter of PhD achievement to continue my teaching job. It is also a matter of notify you that I am not getting my PhD scholarship/any fund since July 2022, but I am full time involved with my study, research & publication under the limitation whatever I notified through robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au

Could you please also advise me that what should I do to submit my final PhD thesis, to receive PhD degree under your supervision. I also requested for third milestone review but I didn't get any response from school administration. Please tell me that what should I do?

I have attached two file whatever I achieved during my PhD candidature.

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936097>

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD school, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936303>

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Thanks for your every consideration & action for my PhD degree.

Best Regards

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Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Robert Shanks

Mon, Aug 28 at 9:40 AM

Dear Professor,

Today I telephoned and tried to communicate with you and Professor Lijing.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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Show original message

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Robert Shanks

Cc: Robert Shanks, Lijing wang

Mon, Aug 28 at 9:42 AM

Dear Professor Robert,

Today I telephoned and tried to communicate with you and Professor Lijing.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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Robert Shanks <robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Wed, Aug 30 at 8:19 AM

RMIT Classification: Trusted

I no longer work at RMIT, I am not able to be a supervisor. I still have my email for this time.

Robert

Em. Prof. Dr Robert Shanks
Emeritus Professor, Polymer Science
School of Science
Science, Engineering and Health
RMIT University
GPO Box 2476 Melbourne, Vic, 3001
Tel 03 9925 1950; Mobile 0400 104 095 day

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>

ISI Thompson Reuters: <http://www.researcherid.com/rid/A-1496-2011>

Scopus ID: 35567552200

<http://scholar.google.com.au/citations?hl=en&user=5WwwxngAAAAJ>

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

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To: Robert Shanks, Robert Shanks

Cc: Lijing Wang, Md Hossain, Andrea Eckersley, Scott Mayson, Safer Community, Sean Ryan, mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au, SHADI HOUSHYAR, Steve Michielsen, Xin Wang, alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au, calum Drummond, Vice Chancellor, researchfellowships@rmit.edu.au, Denise Cuthbert, Saniyat Islam, Shelley MacRae, alice.payne@rmit.edu.au, rts-dscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.au, SGR Scholarships, Sarah Palmer, robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au, RMIT Connect, rusu@rmit.edu.au, Academic Registrar, engranowar06@gmail.com, dvcr@rmit.com.au, gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au, RMIT University, David Castle, alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au Hide

Wed, Aug 30 at 11:40 AM

Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks

RMIT University

Seeking clarification for the post of associate supervisor. May I request to finish the PhD candidature of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher ID: 3820066

Dear Professor,

I hope that you are fine. I am happy that your school e-mail ID is now activated. I am still happy that I got below e-mail from your school e-mail ID.

I am reporting you regularly and regularly. You know very well about my research progress and research conditions. This is my very ending moment of my PhD thesis submission. We had a lot of face-to-face meeting. We had a lot of e-mail communication under the limitation of PhD candidature. I faced life-threatening conspiracy in PhD school again and again through Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye. I reported you for your professional concern although you are a busy professor of RMIT University. Officially, you are my associate supervisor still now. Professionally please let me know if you are facing any verbal threat to continue for the post of associate supervisor. I will be so much happy, I will be so much grateful, I will be so much

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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

beneficial if you can finish my PhD candidature whatever I wanted throughout my PhD candidature.

If you cannot work with RMIT or any concern authority of RMIT university is making any issue to create artificial PhD harassment of Md. Anowar Hossain, I may have right to know officially when I have invested a lot of time and a lot of Australian Dollar to complete the right requirement of PhD degree. Still now, I am working full time under full time study leave to satisfy the PhD requirement of RMIT University. If someone threat to you, he will leave the university, you will supervise your PhD student, nobody can cease your job until you can continue until you can have a minimum time until you are happy to supervise PhD student. I will try to ensure all facilities through the right support/safety of Australian Government if you can present a true voice, otherwise nobody can understand whatever you are thinking whatever trouble you are facing to supervise your PhD student, to present your true voice of PhD supervision.

I am working and planning to go Australian court. The harassment of life-threatening should be considered a separate part of PhD work whatever I reported through the below link.

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286821>

Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286788>

This is also my PhD harassment if are you planning to resign from the post of Associate Supervisor of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher ID: 3820066; you need to notify, clarify, signify and explain by showing actual reason, ethical reason, professional reason, professorship reason as per Australian Quality of Research Framework when I am connected

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

with you since 2020. Your resignation letter will be attached with my PhD thesis in terms of PhD harassment and PhD Progress report. So, you need to send two letters to your PhD candidate if you want to resign from the supervision post of associate supervisor, such as:

✓ You need to send a letter by signing and showing appropriate reason of resignation from the post of associate supervisor; if you have no time, I may draft for you if you permit accordingly.

✓ You need to send a letter by signing and explaining PhD progress report of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; if you have no time, I may draft for you if you permit accordingly.

If you cannot issue two letters from your office by fifteen days, you will get my e-mail for your concern of PhD supervision as per Australian Quality of Research Framework.

This is also being notified that the post of associate supervisor may be vacant during my final PhD thesis submission, and nobody will be replaced for your post to receive Australian Dollar. I will also get advice from school/university administration. I suggest that you should receive your salary as you supervised and edited my PhD works, otherwise I will not be happy.

Thanks for your every ethical support to satisfy the citizenship requirement of Australian Government, to satisfy professor community all over the world, to satisfy Australian Quality of Research Framework, to satisfy the norms of PhD supervisor, to satisfy the norms of Australian PhD school, to satisfy for the peace of mankind.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Draft submission to Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks if he is planning to stop PhD supervision due to his personal limitation, notified to PhD student on 30 August 2023; supervision started on February 2020

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Robert Shanks,Robert Shanks

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Robert Shanks,Robert Shanks

Cc:Lijing Wang,Md Hossain,Andrea Eckersley,Scott Mayson,Safer Community,Sean Ryan,mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au,SHADI HOUSHYAR,Steve Michielsen,Xin Wang,alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au,calum Drummond,Denise Cuthbert,rts-dscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.au,SGR Scholarships,Saniyat Islam,Shelley MacRae,Vice Chancellor,Sarah Palmer,robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au,RMIT Connect,rusu@rmit.edu.au,alice.payne@rmit.edu.au,Academic Registrar,engranowar06@gmail.com,dvcr@rmit.com.au,gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au,RMIT University,David Castle,engranowar@gmail.comHide

Wed, Aug 30 at 12:49 PM

Dear Professor,

I have attached a draft letter (both word & pdf file) for your kind signature if you are planning to stop PhD supervision due to your personal limitation, But I am also happy and happy if you can continue until final PhD thesis submission.

Concern administration is being hardly requested for the right payment of Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, associate supervisor under the RMIT compliance policy applied to him when Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks supervised February 2020 to still now.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thanks for your every support during my PhD candidature under the limitation of COVID-19 & conspiracy of life-threatening of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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BMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Em. Prof. Dr Robert Shanks
Emeritus Professor, Polymer Science
School of Science
Science, Engineering and Health
RMIT University
GPO Box 2476 Melbourne, Vic, 3001
Tel 03 9925 1950; Mobile 0400 104 095 day
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>
ISI Thompson Reuters: <http://www.researcherid.com/rid/A-1496-2011>
Scopus ID: 35567552200
<http://scholar.google.com.au/citations?hl=en&user=5WwwwxngAAAAJ>

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

This is being declared that I am unable to supervise PhD student due to my personal limitation. I supervised Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University since February 2020 to still now. His PhD thesis is entitled “Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds”. So far I supervised, Md. Anowar Hossain is completed PhD requirement to satisfy PhD degree, DR213, PhD (Fashion & Textiles), School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. His invention & PhD research outcomes have been mentioned in below:

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286832>
Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286821>
Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286788>

I wish him every success in his research career for the peace of mankind.

(Signature)

Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks

Associate Supervisor of Md. Anowar Hossain, ID: 3820066

Copy to

Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066

Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor of Md. Anowar Hossain, ID: 3820066

Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate Dean, Research & Innovation, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Office of Academic Registrar, RMIT University

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Communication with law firm, Melbourne, Australia

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enqr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:info@MantooLawyers.com.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:29 PM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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Thanks

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Page | 129

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: info@elvinlawyers.com.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:31 PM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:info@rrlawyers.com.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:36 PM

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Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thanks

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Page | 131

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: info@berrillwatson.com.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:39 PM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and

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[future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](#)

Thanks

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:awb@awblegal.net.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:41 PM

Dear Lawyer,

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engranowar06@gmail.com

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:solicitors@gotocourt.com.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:45 PM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:admin@blossomlawyers.com.au

Thu, Aug 17 at 1:55 PM

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Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; PhD Training (Fashion & Textiles), PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles) since 2010

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

For details biography and profile,

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>, www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of
presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the
world]

Sharon Momoh <admin@blossomlawyers.com.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Cc: Holly Mylne

Fri, Aug 18 at 8:37 AM

Dear Anowar,

Thank you for your recent enquiry. Unfortunately, we do not currently have capacity to take on your matter.

You can however contact the Law Institute of Victoria on 03 9607 9311 who may be able to refer you to a solicitor who can assist you in your matter.

Please note we are not currently retained to act for you, nor are we instructed to take any steps to protect your current position. We do recommend that you seek advice as soon as possible and ensure that any timeframes are met, otherwise you may be prevented from taking any action that may be available to you.

We apologise for not being able to assist you and we wish you well with your matter.

Kind regards

Sharon Momoh | Junior Legal Secretary

P. (07) 5636 5598

E. admin@blossomlawyers.com.au

W. www.blossomlawyers.com.au

A. Suite 1, 42 Thomas Drive, Surfers Paradise QLD
4217

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: enquiries@emwllp.com

Thu, Aug 17 at 2:01 PM

Dear Lawyer,

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Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enagr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:inquiries@liv.asn.au

Fri, Aug 18 at 10:24 AM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thanks

Victim impact statement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University

Page | 139

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: administration@fcl.org.au

Fri, Aug 18 at 11:25 AM

Dear Lawyer,

The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh.

Please if you can advise me if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if I can protect my PhD degree and PhD funding. I have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne. I was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but I am long term sufferer now and I have no way to get Australian court and policing support directly.

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; [PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402)

Thanks

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:visa.assurance@homeaffairs.gov.au

Cc:Vice Chancellor,alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au,Safer Community,Lijing Wang,Robert Shanks,Robert Shanks,SGR Scholarships,Md Hossain,Scott Mayson,Sean Ryan,SHADI HOUSHYAR,Steve Michielsen,Saniyat Islam,Shelley MacRae,Sarah Palmer,student.rights@rmit.edu.au,calum Drummond,Denise Cuthbert,David Castle,DVC R&I,Andrea Eckersley,alice.payne@rmit.edu.au,Academic Registrar,amber.douglas@rmit.edu.au,RMIT Connect,Xin Wang,robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au,rusu@rmit.edu.au,complaintsadvise@rmit.edu.au,Grants,gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au,BRUNSWICK-UNI-OIC,mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au,engranowar06@gmail.com,hotline@nationalsecurity.gov.au,Na hid Islam,RMIT University,NOSSC-CANBERRA,Education - International Students,Complaints,OSHC Medibank,oshc_support@medibank.com.au,complaints@education.gov.au,esos@rmit.edu.au,researchfellowships@rmit.edu.au,registry@hcourt.gov.au,supportservices@supcourt.vic.gov.au,criminal.division.administrators@countycourt.vic.gov.au,CSV-CCV-SRL (CSV),contact@austbar.asn.au,karien.dekker@rmit.edu.au,rt-dscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.auHide

Tue, Sep 12 at 11:16 AM

The Hon Clare O'Neil MP

Minister

Department of Home affairs, Australia

This e-mail has online link for a copy of letter in PDF form.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Dear delegate of Minister,

May I Seek ethical support for activation of student VISA to eliminate PhD harassment when PhD harassment and life-threatening conspiracy of PhD candidate, ID: 3820066 are being forwarded to Australian Court, Australian human rights commission, and chief authorities aligned with PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening again and again.

Page | 141

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336839>

This letter has been forwarded as per office order and response requirement of 28 days.

Thanks for your every ethical support to serve for the peace of mankind.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

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Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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engranowar06@gmail.com

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

PhD Harassment for conference Presentation

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain, legalservices@rmit.edu.au

Cc:Vice Chancellor,Robert Shanks,Lijing Wang,Md Hossain,Andrea Eckersley,Scott Mayson,Sean Ryan,Safer Community,mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au,SHADI HOUSHYAR,Steve Michielsen,Xin Wang,alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au,Denise Cuthbert,calum Drummond,Saniyat Islam,Shelley MacRae,SGR Scholarships,Sarah Palmer,alice.payne@rmit.edu.au,RMIT

Connect,rusu@rmit.edu.au,robyn.healy@rmit.edu.au,Academic

Registrar,engranowar06@gmail.com,dvcr@rmit.com.au,rts-

dscresearchservicecentre@rmit.edu.au,gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au,David Castle,Robert Shanks,Grants,researchfellowships@rmit.edu.au,complaints@rmit.edu.au,Visa Assurance,Education - International StudentsHide

Wed, Sep 20 at 9:11 PM

Ana

Program Manager | MAT-2023

Rogers

In response of below e-mail, I would like to mention following link to satisfy the email response of legalservices@rmit.edu.au in terms of ongoing PhD harassment.

Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320778>

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336839>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

As this is the RMIT affiliated research output, I should ethically mention RMIT affiliation. I am still serving (full time) for RMIT University to satisfy the legal part of PhD degree.

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, **Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street**

Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schoolin...

PhD education and research plays a vital role for the society development. The life-threatening, hidden life-thr...

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT

University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, **Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick**

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engranowar06@gmail.com

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first ve...

The invention of PhD thesis has camouflage theory, color engineering, camoufflage engineering, camouflage materia...

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Hide original message

On Wednesday, September 20, 2023 at 06:40:33 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsscience@magnusconference.com> wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

I hope you're having a wonderful day!

We have received an email from legalservices@rmit.edu.au stating that you are no longer associated with RMIT University, Australia.

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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

To keep our records up-to-date, we kindly ask for your updated affiliation details. Your timely response will help us ensure the accuracy of our records.

Looking forward to hear from you.

Regards

Ana
Conference Manager

Rogers

Conference Correspondence for Presentation of PhD Outcome, RMIT University

5TH EDITION OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Lijing Wang,Robert Shanks,Robert Shanks,Andrea Eckersley,Scott Mayson,Sean Ryan,mac.ferguson@rmit.edu.au,SHADI HOUSHYAR,Steve Michielsen,Xin Wang,alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au,calum Drummond,Denise Cuthbert,Saniyat Islam,Shelley MacRae,gerard.kerlin@rmit.edu.au,karien.dekker@rmit.edu.auHide

Wed, Sep 13 at 5:07 PM

Dear Professor/Dr./Scientist,

I have attached time schedule of presentation for

5TH EDITION OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

Thanks for your participation.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

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Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

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Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

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Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Response needed: Final program: MAT 2023

Yahoo/Sent

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsscience@magnusconference.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sat, Sep 23 at 12:35 PM

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Hope you are having great day!

As we did not received any acknowledgement for the final program and Zoom meeting credentials sent on Sep-13, Please find the attached Final program and consider the below **Zoom meeting login Details to join the event virtually:**

Zoom Meeting

Link: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81569363472?pwd=N1ITOEwwT2pWQ0J6Y1c3M3RMV01CZz09>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Meeting ID: 815 6936 3472

Passcode: 037521

Looking forward to your early response. Kindly acknowledge this mail.

Awaits your response.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Sent: September 20th, 2023 06:10 PM
To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Subject: RE: Regarding Affiliation: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Dear Anowar Hossain,

I hope you're having a wonderful day!

We have received an email from legalservices@rmit.edu.au stating that you are no longer associated with RMIT University, Australia.

To keep our records up-to-date, we kindly ask for your updated affiliation details. Your timely response will help us ensure the accuracy of our records.

Looking forward to hear from you.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Sent: September 12th, 2023 04:02 PM

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Subject: RE: PPT received: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for your mail.

We have received your PPT slides of your oral presentation.

We will keep you updated regarding PPT details shortly.

Looking forward to see you on screen.

Regards

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: September 12th, 2023 12:35 PM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: PPT request: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Dear Organizer,

I have attached presentation slides in the below link.

Md Anowar Hossain. (2023, August 29). Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds. 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Olympia Hotel, Events & Spa Carrer Mestre Serrano, 5, 46120 Alborai, Valencia, Spain. Zenodo.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298582>

Please download by next three days, I have kept the file open access.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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On Thursday, September 7, 2023 at 07:46:36 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Sorry for the inconvenience caused. We are unable to download the PPT.

Kindly share as attachment through mail or via We transfer: <https://wetransfer.com/>

Feel free to revert for further assistance.

Looking forward to your submission.

Regards

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: September 2nd, 2023 06:17 PM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Follow up: PPT request: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Dear Organizer,

Please notify me after downloading the ppt. file. I will keep it close access after your notification.

Best Regards

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

On Saturday, September 2, 2023 at 05:22:27 PM GMT+6, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Dear Organizer,

I have attached presentation slides in below link.

Md Anowar Hossain. (2023, August 29). Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds. 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Olympia Hotel, Events & Spa Carrer Mestre Serrano, 5, 46120 Alboraiia, Valencia, Spain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.829858>

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.

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Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

On Friday, September 1, 2023 at 06:11:28 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

This is a gentle reminder from MAT-2023.

Kindly submit your Oral presentation in PPT slides format. Time allocated for each presentation is 20 minutes. We will provide you the Final program and Zoom Meeting invitation including login credentials with link 2-3 days prior to the event.

Do not hesitate to contact us for any details.

Looking forward for your participation.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Sent: June 6th, 2023 06:54 PM
To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Subject: RE: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for your mail.

In response to your query, we would like to inform you that, Meeting link and exact date/time slot of your presentation will be available 20 days prior to the conference start date after finalizing the program.

We will keep you updated about the conference.

For any more queries, feel free to contact us.

Have a great day.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: June 6th, 2023 04:44 PM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Follow up: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Thanks for your update about confirmation of registration and slot of presentation. Could you please let me the right schedule with online link for virtual presentation?

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles) since 2010

Research Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia,

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

For details biography and profile,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>, www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

On Monday, June 5, 2023 at 04:03:47 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

We haven't heard back from you since our last conversation.

As per your mail, we would like to inform you that your slot for the event has already been confirmed by our committee, so there is no need for you to register again.

Should you have any queries, feel free to contact us.

Regards

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: May 2nd, 2023 09:37 PM
To: materialsscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Ana Rogers Conference Manager

I am unable to proceed free of cost virtual registration. Could you please send me the exact link for free of cost registration?

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, **PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).**

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On Tuesday, May 2, 2023 at 12:33:53 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for getting back to us.

Considering your eminence in the field, our committee is happy to provide you with free virtual registration.

Please let us know if you have any questions.

Awaits to hearing from you!

Regards

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: April 4th, 2023 09:19 AM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

I am sorry to notify that I have no fund for conference presentation. I would like to request again for free of cost registration.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

It is also a matter that you already disagreed to pay speaking fees under the decision of committee.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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On Thursday, March 30, 2023 at 05:25:36 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for getting back to us.

Our committee is happy to provide you with the special discount and the least minimal charge to confirm your slot is \$100. I hope this special discount helps you with your participation.

To avail this special discount use the mentioned mail id (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) along with the other details in the registration form. <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/register>

Please let us know if you have any questions.

Looking forward to hearing from you!

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: March 29th, 2023 09:22 PM
To: materials@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

I briefly notified for the concern of conference committee that I have no funding in this moment of my professional journey. So I would like to

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

seek 100% discount for registration, confirmation and virtual participation.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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On Wednesday, March 29, 2023 at 07:11:09 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for getting back to us.

By considering your financial concern our committee is happy to provide you with **50%** discount on your **registration charges**. Being a self funded organization with limited external funds we are unable to support you completely hope you can understand our limitations.

To avail this discount use the mentioned mail id (**engr.anowar@yahoo.com**) along with the other details in the registration form. <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/register>

Kindly get back to us if you have any issues!

Awaits to hearing from you!

Regards

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: March 29th, 2023 08:45 AM
To: materials@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Abstract Acknowledgement: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Program Manager | MAT-2023

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engranowar06@gmail.com

Presentation on "Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds"

As per below e-mail, I would like to participate in virtual presentation. Could you please confirm my free of cost registration for the session of material science and engineering? I have tried for registration, but I am unable to continue with free of cost registration.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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On Tuesday, March 28, 2023 at 06:16:30 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Good day. Hope you are doing great.

I am pleased to inform that your abstract entitled “**Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds**” has been reviewed and is accepted for the **5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering (Scopus Indexed Event)**. Please let us know your type and mode of presentation. i.e, **Oral Presentation (In-Person/Virtual) or Poster Presentation (In-Person/Virtual)**.

We appreciate that your paper addresses the key advancements in the field of Materials Science and we’re excited to hear more from you on this.

As of now, we request you to register at our website link: <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/register> and confirm your participation at the earliest.

Please feel free to email me with any questions.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

From: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Sent: March 24th, 2023 06:18 PM
To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Subject: RE: Abstract under review process: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Page | 169

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Greetings of the day.

We have received your abstract entitled “**Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds**” and a team of experts are reviewing it. We will update you about the status shortly.

Please let us know your type and mode of presentation. i.e, **Oral Presentation (In-Person/Virtual) or Poster Presentation (In-Person/Virtual).**

According to your query regarding stipend we are unable to provide you with travel and accommodation charges. Whereas we can support you with registration charges.

If you require any further information, feel free to contact me.

Regards

Ana Rogers

Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: March 19th, 2023 11:10 PM
To: material-science@mgconference.com
Subject: Re: Hi Anowar Hossain, You are invited to be a part of this event

To

The Chairperson

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Organizing Committee of 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering Valencia, Spain

Regarding notification of speaker at MAT-2023 during September 25-27, 2023

Dear Respected Sir,

Thanks for your proposal letter to be speaker at MAT-2023. I am happy to participate as per invitation.

I would like to notify my field of research for your concern of next stage decision and confirmation. My research work has been focused on “Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”.

I have attached my proposed title, abstract and biography for your consideration. Please let me know and clarify me in detail if I am eligible for presentation of MAT-2023.

May I ask to pay ‘speaking stipend’ to compensate for my ongoing research cost including the whole cost of conference presentation relates to registration, accommodation and air ticket.

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of Linkedin Profile

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Research gate profile

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

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On Tuesday, December 27, 2022 at 07:15:07 AM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain

Greetings for the day. Hope you are fine.

We are extremely pleased to announce our **“5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering”** which will be a Hybrid Event with an option of online attendance. The conference will be taking place in **Valencia, Spain** slated during **September 25-27, 2023** and will emphasize the theme *“Exceeding Vision in Materials Science and Engineering through Novel Innovations.”*

We are highly impressed by your research profile and we believe that your contribution to the field of Materials Science is unparalleled and it would be an absolute honour for us if you would join us as a Speaker at MAT-2023.

We highly recommend you visit our website and check the details related to the conference.

For complete information, visit the [Conference Website](#)

This worldwide scientific gathering will examine the most disruptive trends in Materials Science, as well as emerging trends and issues. It is critical to participate in conversations and cross-border learning in order to keep up with the current advances. The organizing committee has put up a robust programme that includes poster sessions, keynote sessions and networking events which will be beneficial to both onsite and online attendees and delegates.

Your acknowledgement of this email will be highly remarkable and we request you to submit your title of talk as a positive acknowledgement.

I do very much hope that you will be able to accept this invitation.

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
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Please do not hesitate to contact me for any further information.

Yours sincerely

Ana Rogers

Program Manager | MAT-2023

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Your Abstract Presentation at World Congress on MATERIAL SCIENCE AND NANOTECHNOLOGY, JULY 10-11, 2023 |Virtual Eventz

Yahoo/Sent

Journal of Materials and Polymer Science (ISSN 2832-9384) <editor.jmps@uniscience-news.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Mon, Sep 25 at 10:12 AM

Hello Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain,

We found your research profile at [World Congress on MATERIAL SCIENCE AND NANOTECHNOLOGY, JULY 10-11, 2023 | Virtual Event](#).

Your research, titled " [An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm](#) ", is relevant to our [Journal of Materials and Polymer Science \(ISSN 2832-9384\)](#), and we'd be happy to publish it, if you're interested.

Please submit a full-length article to this email.
Feel free to contact us for additional information and details.

Sincerely,
Sophia Angelina,
Managing Editor.
WhatsApp: +13362217080

Follow up: PPT request: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event
Yahoo/Inbox

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsscience@magnusconference.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Fri, Sep 1 at 6:11 PM

Dear Anowar Hossain,
This is a gentle reminder from MAT-2023.

Kindly submit your Oral presentation in PPT slides format. Time allocated for each presentation is 20 minutes. We will provide you the Final program and Zoom Meeting invitation including login credentials with link 2-3 days prior to the event.

Do not hesitate to contact us for any details.

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Looking forward for your participation.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

RE: PPT received: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Yahoo/Inbox

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsscience@magnusconference.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Tue, Sep 12 at 4:32 PM

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for your mail.

We have received your PPT slides of your oral presentation.

We will keep update you regarding PPT details shortly.

Looking forward to see you on screen.

Regards

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsscience@magnusconference.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Tue, Apr 4 at 7:09 PM

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for getting back to us.

Considering your eminence in the field, our committee is happy to provide you with **free virtual registration**.

Please let us know if you have any questions.

Awaits to hearing from you!

Regards

Ana Rogers

Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: April 4th, 2023 09:19 AM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers

Conference Manager

I am sorry to notify that I have no fund for conference presentation. I would like to request again for free of cost registration.

It is also a matter that you already disagreed to pay speaking fees under the decision of committee.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

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Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
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Research Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia,

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

For details biography and profile, ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world

On Thursday, March 30, 2023 at 05:25:36 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for getting back to us.

Our committee is happy to provide you with the special discount and the least minimal charge to confirm your slot is \$100. I hope this special discount helps you with your participation.

To avail this special discount use the mentioned mail id (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) along with the other details in the registration form. <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/register>

Please let us know if you have any questions.

Looking forward to hearing from you!

Regards

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: March 29th, 2023 09:22 PM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

I briefly notified for the concern of conference committee that I have no funding in this moment of my professional journey. So I would like to seek 100% discount for registration, confirmation and virtual participation.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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On Wednesday, March 29, 2023 at 07:11:09 PM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thank you for getting back to us.

By considering your financial concern our committee is happy to provide you with **50%** discount on your **registration charges**. Being a self funded organization with limited external funds we are unable to support you completely hope you can understand our limitations.

To avail this discount use the mentioned mail id (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) along with the other details in the registration form. <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/register>

Kindly get back to us if you have any issues!

Awaits to hearing from you!

Regards

Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Sent: March 29th, 2023 08:45 AM
To: materialscience@magnusconference.com
Subject: Re: Abstract Acknowledgement: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Ana Rogers

Program Manager | MAT-2023

Presentation on "Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds"

As per below e-mail, I would like to participate in virtual presentation. Could you please confirm my free of cost registration for the session of material science and engineering? I have tried for registration, but I am unable to continue with free of cost registration.

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile
Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law,
Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation,
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all over the world]**

RE: Regarding registration: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Yahoo/Inbox

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsconference.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Wed, Aug 9 at 12:39 PM

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Wishing you a Good day!

We would like to request you to check your website profile and check for any
modifications/errors, link: <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/speaker/anowar-hossain>

Kindly submit your Oral presentation in PPT slides format. Time allocated for each presentation is 20
minutes. We will provide you the Final program and Zoom Meeting invitation including login
credentials with link 2-3 days prior to the event.

Do not hesitate to contact us for any details.

Looking forward for your participation.

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Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manage

RE: Abstract Acknowledgement: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Yahoo/Inbox

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsconference@magnusconference.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Tue, Mar 28 at 6:16 PM

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Good day. Hope you are doing great.

I am pleased to inform that your abstract entitled “**Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds**” has been reviewed and is accepted for the **5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering (Scopus Indexed Event)**. Please let us know your type and mode of presentation. i.e, **Oral Presentation (In-Person/Virtual) or Poster Presentation (In-Person/Virtual)**.

We appreciate that your paper addresses the key advancements in the field of Materials Science and we’re excited to hear more from you on this.

As of now, we request you to register at our website link: <https://materials.magnusconferences.com/register> and confirm your participation at the earliest.

Please feel free to email me with any questions.

Regards
Ana Rogers
Conference Manager

RE: Abstract under review process: MAT 2023 | Hybrid Event

Yahoo/Inbox

Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain <materialsconference@magnusconference.com>

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Fri, Mar 24 at 6:48 PM

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Greetings of the day.

We have received your abstract entitled “**Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds**” and a team of experts are reviewing it. We will update you about the status shortly.

Please let us know your type and mode of presentation. i.e, **Oral Presentation (In-Person/Virtual) or Poster Presentation (In-Person/Virtual).**

According to your query regarding stipend we are unable to provide you with travel and accommodation charges. Whereas we can support you with registration charges.

If you require any further information, feel free to contact me.

Regards

Ana Rogers

Conference Manager

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sent: March 19th, 2023 11:10 PM

To: material-science@mgconference.com

Subject: Re: Hi Anowar Hossain, You are invited to be a part of this event

To

The Chairperson

Organizing Committee of 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering Valencia, Spain

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Regarding notification of speaker at MAT-2023 during September 25-27, 2023

Dear Respected Sir,

Thanks for your proposal letter to be speaker at MAT-2023. I am happy to participate as per invitation.

I would like to notify my field of research for your concern of next stage decision and confirmation. My research work has been focused on “Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”.

I have attached my proposed title, abstract and biography for your consideration. Please let me know and clarify me in detail if I am eligible for presentation of MAT-2023.

May I ask to pay ‘speaking stipend’ to compensate for my ongoing research cost including the whole cost of conference presentation relates to registration, accommodation and air ticket.

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of Linkedin Profile

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Research gate profile

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

Best Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part, PhD Student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles) since 2010

Research Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia,

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

For details biography and profile, ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairstanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

On Tuesday, December 27, 2022 at 07:15:07 AM GMT+6, Materials Science 2023 | Valencia, Spain wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain

Greetings for the day. Hope you are fine.

We are extremely pleased to announce our **"5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering"** which will be a Hybrid Event with an option of online

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

attendance. The conference will be taking place in **Valencia, Spain** slated during **September 25-27, 2023** and will emphasize the theme *“Exceeding Vision in Materials Science and Engineering through Novel Innovations.”*

We are highly impressed by your research profile and we believe that your contribution to the field of Materials Science is unparalleled and it would be an absolute honour for us if you would join us as a Speaker at MAT-2023.

We highly recommend you visit our website and check the details related to the conference.

For complete information, visit the [Conference Website](#)

This worldwide scientific gathering will examine the most disruptive trends in Materials Science, as well as emerging trends and issues. It is critical to participate in conversations and cross-border learning in order to keep up with the current advances. The organizing committee has put up a robust programme that includes poster sessions, keynote sessions and networking events which will be beneficial to both onsite and online attendees and delegates.

Your acknowledgement of this email will be highly remarkable and we request you to submit your title of talk as a positive acknowledgement.

I do very much hope that you will be able to accept this invitation.

Please do not hesitate to contact me for any further information.

Yours sincerely

Ana Rogers

Program Manager | MAT-2023

Email: material-science@scientific-meetings.com

Phone: + 1 (702) 988-2320

WhatsApp: +1 (540) 709-1879

150 South Wacker Drive #2400
Chicago, IL 60606, USA

Philippine Textile Congress 2023⁶

Yahoo/Inbox

Rey Eliseo Torrejos <rectorrejos@dost.gov.ph>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Tue, Oct 3 at 1:34 PM

Hi Prof. Anowar Hossain,

We are organizing the 2nd iteration of the Philippine Textile Congress (PTC 2023).

This is a virtual platform for converging and integrating various Philippine Textile Innovation ecosystem stakeholders which will be held on November 7-24, 2023.

Last year's Philippine Textile Congress was a success with 60+ invited speakers from different countries resulting in over 800+ participants per session.

You can check the highlights of last year's congress through our official website (philippinetextilecongress.com).

This year's theme, "*Futures Thinking Philippine Textiles*", strives to encourage cross-disciplinary and holistic ideas through the exploration of trends and drivers for change in the Philippine and Global Textile Industry.

In this regard, we are hoping that you can share your work on textile-based camouflage systems and be one of the speakers for the session on Textile for Human Security and Defense, which will be held virtually on November 20, 2023. We will be sending you the official invitation letter along with the details of the congress in the next few days.

Thanks and we are hoping for your positive response.

Best regards,

Rey

--

Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos, Ph.D.

Associate Scientist

Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI)

Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Rey Eliseo Torrejos

Wed, Oct 4 at 11:35 AM

Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos, Ph.D.

Associate Scientist

Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI)

Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO)

General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631

Dear Organizer,

Thanks for your information of conference.

I am planning to present on camouflage system.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

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Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India & Australia)

Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, **Mobile:** +8801788396264

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Show original message

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Rey Eliseo Torrejos

Thu, Oct 5 at 1:00 PM

Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos, Ph.D.

Associate Scientist

Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI)

Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO)

General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631

Dear Organizer,

It is OK for me if you have a zoom meeting tomorrow.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

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Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

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E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

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Rey Eliseo Torrejos <rectorrejos@dost.gov.ph>

To: Anowar Hossain

Thu, Oct 5 at 1:07 PM

Hi Prof. Anowar,

Can we meet via Zoom tomorrow at around 11:30 AM (AEST) Australia time>?

I will send you the Zoom link.

best regards,

Rey

Show original message

--

Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos, Ph.D.

Associate Scientist

Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI)

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO)

General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: Rey Eliseo Torrejos

Thu, Oct 5 at 1:21 PM

Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos, Ph.D.

Associate Scientist

Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI)

Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO)

General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631

Dear Dr. Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos,

Your proposed time is convenient for me.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

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Rey Eliseo Torrejos <rectorrejos@dost.gov.ph>

To: Anowar Hossain

Fri, Oct 6 at 7:22 AM

Hi Prof. Anowar,

Here's the zoom link for today's zoom meeting in a while.

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83590804358?pwd=Sm5yL2hxc2VFWWRVbWw0U2FRbDJndz09>

best regards,

Rey

Show original message

Rey Eliseo C. Torrejos, Ph.D.

Associate Scientist

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI)

Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO)

General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631

Invitation: Meeting with Prof. Anowar Hossain @ Fri 6 Oct 2023 10am - 11am (PST) (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Yahoo/Inbox

Meeting with Prof. Anowar Hossain

[View on Calendar](#)

When

8:00 AM - 9:00 AM

Who

4 guests invited

Are you going? [Yes](#) [Maybe](#) [No](#)

rdd.ptri.dost@gmail.com <rdd.ptri.dost@gmail.com>

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, rectorrejos@dost.gov.ph, josepaolo.bantang@ptri.dost.gov.ph

Fri, Oct 6 at 7:31 AM

RDD Virtual Conference Center

Zoom Details: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83590804358?pwd=Sm5yL2hxc2VFWWRVbWw0U2FRbDJndz09>

Meeting ID: 835 9080 4358

Passcode: 372119

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BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

When

Friday 6 Oct 2023 · 10am – 11am (Philippine Standard Time)

Guests

rdd.ptri.dost@gmail.com- organiser
rectorrej@ptri.dost.gov.ph
engr.anowar@yahoo.com
josepaolo.bantang@ptri.dost.gov.ph

Correspondence with Dean, School of Engineering, RMIT University

May I get PhD degree from your school if there is any norms/guideline to satisfy the PhD requirement from your school.

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au

Cc:

mark.sanderson@rmit.edu.au,

margaret.jollands@rmit.edu.au,

jennifer.palmer2@rmit.edu.au,

elena.pirogova@rmit.edu.au,

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namita.choudhury@rmit.edu.au

kevin.zhang@rmit.edu.au

james.scott@rmit.edu.au

reza.hoseinnezhad@rmit.edu.au

stuart.bateman@rmit.edu.au

sara.moridpour@rmit.edu.au

Hide

Fri, Sep 29 at 2:59 PM

Professor Ray Kirby

Dear Professor,

I have completed first and second milestone from school of fashion & textiles, RMIT University. I have also sole-author publication from school of fashion & textiles, RMIT University. May I get PhD degree from your school if there is any norms/guideline to satisfy the PhD requirement from your school?

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, [Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048)

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first ve...

The invention of PhD thesis has camouflage theory, color engineering, camouflage engineering, camouflage materia...

Present condition of PhD candidature has been mentioned through below link

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286821>

Thanks for your kind feedback.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong

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Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.

Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Consultant

(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Nobody can cease your dream, if you are determined for highest climbing, **a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University.**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Laboratory correspondence for Hyperspectral Camera

Submission of PhD details for your ethical comments and feedback whatever I shortly discussed with you

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: rakib@bau.edu.bd

Tue, Sep 19 at 9:51 AM

Professor Dr. Md. Rakib Hassan
Department of Computer Science & Mathematics
Faculty of Agricultural Engineering & Technology
Bangladesh Agricultural University

Dear Professor,

I would like to refer a casual meeting on 17 September 2023. Therefore, I would like to submit my PhD details for your ethical comments and feedback whatever I shortly discussed with you.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286821>

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, [Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048)

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

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[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

May I seek a free of cost support of hyperspectral scanning of two samples.2

Yahoo/Sent

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: iqbal21155@bau.edu.bd

Cc: Lijing Wang, Robert Shanks, Robert Shanks

Sun, Sep 24 at 11:51 AM

Professor Dr. Abdullah Iqbal

Department of Food Technology and Rural Industries

Bangladesh Agricultural University

Mymensingh-2022, Bangladesh

Dear Professor,

May I seek a free of cost support of hyperspectral scanning of two samples.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Dr. Abdullah Iqbal <iqbal21155@bau.edu.bd>

To: Anowar Hossain

Cc: Lijing Wang, Robert Shanks, Robert Shanks

Sun, Sep 24 at 2:47 PM

Dear Sir,

Thank you very much for your email. Unfortunately, my department does not have any hyperspectral imaging facilities. You most likely read my papers in which I used HSI. During my PhD at University College Dublin (UCD) in Ireland, I used HSI.

With best regards,

=====

Abdullah Iqbal PhD

Professor
Dept. of Food Tech. & Rural Industries
Bangladesh Agricultural University

Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Could you please let me know if Institute of remote sensing has hyperspectral camera?

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: irsgis@juniv.edu

Fri, Sep 29 at 10:29 AM

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker, literary & Science writer; Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Dear Officer,

Could you please let me know if Institute of remote sensing has hyperspectral camera?

Best Regards

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Institute of Remote Sensing and GIS <irsgis@juniv.edu>

To: Anowar Hossain

Sun, Oct 1 at 9:27 AM

Dear Sir,

Good Morning!

Thank you for reaching out for the hyperspectral camera.

We are very sorry that we don't have the hyperspectral camera right now.

Best Regards

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
enranowar06@gmail.com

Krishna Prosad Mondal (On behalf of the IRS Office)

Please may I ask hyperspectral testing charge of four sample

Yahoo/Sent

Page | 217

Anowar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Cc:Lijing Wang,Robert Shanks,Robert Shanks

Sun, Sep 24 at 11:40 AM

Professor (Dr.) Anisur Rahman
Head of the Department
Department of Farm Power and Machinery
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh-2022, Bangladesh

Dear Professor,

I had a casual meeting with you in front of your office on 24 September 2023. As per discussion, I would like to ask the hyperspectral testing charge of two sample.

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship).

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India.

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong

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(Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education)

Motivational speaker & writer since 2007

E-mail: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile: +8801788396264

Visit profile,

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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidency/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Correspondence with Victoria Legal Aid

Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Fri, Sep 29 at 8:10 AM

Chief Executive Officer
Victoria Legal Aid

Dear officer,
I am resending an application of legal support for your approval and necessary action of your office.

Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320778>

Best Regards

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles) PhD Research ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship). Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India. BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

*Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Acknowledgement

Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (**M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain & Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023ap; Hossain et al.; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2019; Samanta et al., 2016) (**Hossain, 2023ai, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023cj, 2023ck**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bo; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bu, 2023bv, 2023bw, 2023bx;

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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting; Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s); PhD application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; acknowledges RMIT University and Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2024.

13 July 2024

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

**Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.**

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/JMP-7353-2023>

<https://sciprofiles.com/profile/1995474>

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237842>

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.

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